

Pilot: Welcome to the show!

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with contributions from Andrea Herdegen, Ignacio Blanquer Espert, Marialuisa Lavitrano, Robert Jones, Sara Garavelli, Sarah Jones, Stefan Hanslik, Suzanne Dumouchel, Volker Beckmann, Wilhelm Widmark (EOSC Board of Directors and EOSC-Pillar Steering Board Representatives)

Marie

When asked “Think of a scientist”, what do you hear?

- ***Publish or perish*** (computer animated voice)
- Oh, you are still working on this paper?
- Is this even the right methodology for what you're trying to do?
- Where are you even getting your funding?
- Aren't you too old to be a PhD student?
- What's your impact?
- ***Publish or perish***
- Are you really passionate about your research field?
- So you would disagree that your results are completely invalid?
- How does it feel to get paid for just trying to see if something works?
- There's a paper disproving your whole concept, did you not read it?!
- *Record scratch*
- ***Publish or perish***

Andreas

Sometimes, it can be quite... challenging.

Marie

In order to work, scientists require a wide range of resources and support - something the European Union has long been working to provide. The vision and mission of “Connecting research across Europe and beyond” can be seen as *the* challenge of the current age.

Andreas

“Connecting research across Europe and beyond”: With this podcast, we'll let you take a peek into the present - and hopefully, the future - of scientific support structures. You'll have an insight into the tools and services developed as part of current EU research, supporting projects designed to make science, its work, its achievements, and its data, more accessible.

I'm Andreas Villarreal

Marie

I'm Marie Czuray and this is - Stories of Data.

Now, to begin, why don't we talk about who we are, and why we started this podcast - Andreas?

Andreas

Yes, thank you! Well, let's see, a word about me: I'm originally from Belgium, moved here, to Vienna, to study political economy and sustainability now well over a decade ago. I've been living here ever since, and am currently working at the Austrian Social Science Data Archive - AUSSDA for our friends - on a project called Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud.

Marie

...SSHOC for friends?

Andreas

Yes, quite right! Now, what SSHOC does is to work on the Social Science and Humanities portion of the European Open Science Cloud. This is the structure where we want European researchers, innovators, companies and citizens to be able to publish, find and re-use data, as well as tools and services for research, innovation, and educational purposes. We're bringing together over 20 partner organisations, and their 27 associates, to create the tools, the training, the infrastructure, and all of it in a FAIR way, a term which stands for the key principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability. How about you?

Marie

Well, after my studies I worked in Copenhagen and Prague in the field of communication and culture and later in Vienna, I was all about business ethics and sustainable finance. Currently I am like Andreas working at the Austrian Social Science Data Archive. And I am as well involved in the development of the European Open Science Cloud (in short: EOSC). But I work for a different project.

Andreas

A project called EOSC-Pillar, right?

Marie

Exactly. EOSC-Pillar reinforces interaction and collaboration on Open Science in Austria, Belgium, France, Germany and Italy. The project gathers representatives of national initiatives in order to coordinate the harmonization of data infrastructures and services. This will support the development and long-term sustainability of the European Open Science Cloud, EOSC for short.

Andreas

And as we were sharing an office together, and talked about our respective research projects, that's when the idea for this podcast series started to take shape!

Marie

What's really interesting is that we realised how bringing in perspectives from both projects allowed us to tell a story: SSHOC and EOSC-Pillar complement each other. They are building on separate, yet related aspects of scientific research and data analysis. EOSC-Pillar builds on the collaboration between actors and initiatives in Open Science on the national level. By using these coordinated resources, EOSC is build further.

Andreas

Precisely! While SSHOC is providing the tools and content from the specific perspective of the Social Sciences, Heritage Sciences, and Humanities. Which means that by covering the two projects, we can see how the EOSC infrastructure is being built both by taking the perspective of already established national actors, and that of specific scientific disciplines.

Marie

SSHOC and EOSC-Pillar are complementing each other and learning from each other. Thanks to the tools, trainings, and services in both projects. This is for sure interesting to explore! So, to summarize - Andreas, what can we look forward to in this podcast series?

Andreas

Well, the idea is to give a voice to the people behind both projects - the developers, the partners, across Europe. We'll hear about their work, their challenges, their needs, their success stories, and about how the European Open Science Cloud can help, and already does.

Marie

And there are quite a lot of stories to tell! I mean, from all over Europe, and in so many different fields!

Andreas

Yeah, there's so much happening in the background of science and academia. And this podcast should be an opportunity to hear these stories.

Marie

And the reason why we called this "Stories of Data".

Andreas

Yes - A lot of the work being done in science depends on the access to research data, and on the tools to work with it in its various forms, which is what both projects are aiming for. And what EOSC as a whole, is trying to facilitate!

Marie

And that's really what this is all about: making the necessary tools for research and its preservation, more accessible in a sustainable way. I'm sure the people we'll talk to for this podcast will have a tale or two on that topic.

Andreas

Now of course, what with the whole pandemic thing happening right now, paying each of them a visit for an in-person interview is not going to be possible-

Marie

Plus, let's not forget the little issue of budget, not to mention reducing our carbon footprint by travelling less.

Andreas

Quite. So this will be more of a virtual road trip, where we'll share with our audience the insights we'll gather from partners all over the continent! And hopefully, by the end we'll have a picture of the work being done, and how everyone, even outside of academia, might benefit, and perhaps even contribute! Who knows, we might be giving some people a few new ideas...

Marie

Sounds promising - I'm looking forward to it!

Andreas

So am I - let's get into it!

Marie

So people out there: Join us for the next episode! And for those of you who are already curious, look up the websites for both projects collaborating on this series.

Andreas

The websites for those are eosc-pillar.eu, and sshopencloud.eu, that's ssh open cloud dot eu, all in one word.

Marie

You'll find news, and events, as well as updates and detailed information about everything we have going on. And what about the website of EOSC? The European Open Science Cloud?

Andreas

Huch, you mean the one and only website for EOSC... that's a tricky question - there isn't really one. That's because EOSC is more than a single project, it is more than the sum of its parts, and encompasses many different processes and perspectives.

Marie

Then perhaps there should be also a podcast on "What's EOSC?" What do you think?

Andreas

Challenge accepted. But perhaps for another time. Still, that should do it for a first overview, don't you think?

Marie

For now, yes! I'm really looking forward to our podcast, and I hope you listeners will join us for that!

Andreas

Until then, take care, stay safe, and stay curious!

Marie

Bye!